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EFFECTS OF PAST AND PRESENT HABITAT ON THE GUT MICROBIOTA OF A WILD RODENT

by

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Supplementary Methods

Before the start of the experiment, all Ugglan Special2 live traps (Grahnb, Sweden) were washed with a Virkon solution (standard dilution of 1%) to reduce microbial contamination, rinsed with clean water, air dried and baited with sunflower seeds and a slice of potato before they were placed on one of the nodes of the square-shaped trapping grids in every forest site (4 x 4, ~20 meter distance between individual traps). Sourcing of wild bank voles was done by trapping for 3 consecutive nights in different subsets of urban and rural forests to decrease temporal bias between the two forest groups and increase the practical feasibility. All traps were checked daily and if occupied traps were replaced (with clean traps washed with Virkon). On the third and last trapping day, all traps were removed. All captured bank voles were directly transferred to 'poo boxes' (*i.e.*, plastic boxes surface-sterilised with ethanol) in the field and transported back to the Animal Facility of the University of Jyväskylä. Fecal samples were taken from all the bank voles immediately upon arrival to the Animal Facilities (*i.e.*, pre-transfer microbiota after initial capture phase, post-transfer microbiota after recapture phase). Tweezers, sterilized by burning and ethanol, were used to collect the fecal pellets from the 'poo boxes' to sterile 1.5 mL tubes. Tubes were immediately put into -20 °C freezer and moved for storage to a -80 °C freezer by the end of the day. Additionally, all animals were tagged with subcutaneous microchips for future identification (only after the initial capture). After fecal sampling, animals were manually examined for gravity status and transferred directly to an individual cage (Makrolon Type III cages (43x26x15 cm)) with bedding material and hay, and were provided with water and standard rodent chow (Avelsfoder för råtta och mus R36; Lactamin, Stockholm, Sweden) *ad libidum*. The initial sourcing phase resulted in 81 experimental pregnant females. Pregnant bank voles were kept in the Animal Facility and checked for parturition once every day. After giving birth, mothers and their newborn pups stayed for 2-3 additional days in the laboratory to ensure recovery before their release into a forest patch that had either the same or opposite treatment (*i.e.*, urban or rural forest site) as their site of origin although they were never released into the original location itself. Every forest patch hosted two transferred mothers with their offspring. Each experimental pair per forest site consisted of one urban and one rural mother with a mismatch between their release dates of maximum 0-6 days. Mothers and newborn offspring were released to the field in their laboratory cages that were provided with food pellets and a slice of potato. In the field, the cage was placed in the middle of the trapping grid and balanced vertically with an open lid so the mother could escape, scout the area, and carry pups to a newly found hiding place in the close vicinity. After the experimental mothers spent 3-4 weeks in their new forest area, we initiated their recapture using the same procedure as described above. This timing was chosen because it coincides with the end of the average nursing period in bank voles. This final experimental phase resulted in the successful recapture of 28 of the experimental adult females. The same field and lab protocol was applied during the final experimental phase as during the initial sourcing phase, except that trapping duration in the field ranged between 3-4 nights to maximize recapture success.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1. Alpha diversity differences between pre-transfer microbiota of urban and rural bank voles

Results from the linear regression models, carried out by the *lm* function in R ($p < 0.05$).

a) ASV Richness

<i>lm (ASV Richness ~ site of origin, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	264.833	25.589	10.350	1.03e-10
Site of origin: U	2.542	33.851	0.075	0.941
F-statistic: 0.005638 on 1 and 26 df, Adjusted R-squared: -0.03824				

b) Shannon Diversity

<i>lm (Shannon Index ~ site of origin, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	5.3367	0.2283	23.377	<2e-16
Site of origin: U	0.1624	0.3020	0.538	0.595
F-statistic: 0.2891 on 1 and 26 df, Adjusted R-squared: -0.02704				

c) Faith's Phylogenetic Diversity

<i>lm (Faith's PD ~ site of origin, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	18.2507	0.8940	20.416	<2e-16
Site of origin: U	-0.1107	1.1826	-0.094	0.926
F-statistic: 0.008756 on 1 and 26 df, Adjusted R-squared: -0.03811				

Supplementary Table S2. Change in Alpha diversity over time within experimental groups

Two-sided paired t-tests were used by implementing the *t.test* function in R to test whether the change in alpha diversity per experimental group was different from zero. Positive values in 'Statistic' mean there was an increase in alpha diversity towards the end of the experiment (alpha diversity (pre-transfer microbiota) < alpha diversity (post-transfer microbiota)) while negative values indicate a decrease between respective groups.

Alpha Diversity	Trtmnt	Group1	Group2	N	Statistic	df	p	P adj
ASV Richness	RurRur	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	7	-0.865	6	0.42	0.539
ASV Richness	UrbRur	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	7	1.01	6	0.349	0.539
ASV Richness	RurUrb	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	5	-0.670	4	0.539	0.539
ASV Richness	UrbUrb	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	9	0.749	8	0.476	0.539
Shannon Diversity	RurRur	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	7	-0.941	6	0.383	0.424
Shannon Diversity	UrbRur	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	7	1.26	6	0.253	0.424
Shannon Diversity	RurUrb	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	5	-1.74	4	0.157	0.424
Shannon Diversity	UrbUrb	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	9	-0.842	8	0.424	0.424
Faith's PD	RurRur	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	7	0.00543	6	0.996	0.996
Faith's PD	UrbRur	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	7	0.962	6	0.373	0.807
Faith's PD	RurUrb	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	5	-0.695	4	0.526	0.807
Faith's PD	UrbUrb	Pre-transfer	Post-transfer	9	0.538	8	0.605	0.807

Supplementary Table S3. Pairwise differences in alpha diversity change between experimental groups

Results from the linear regression models, carried out by the *lm* function in R ($p < 0.05$). This method was used to test whether the change in alpha diversity between the pre-transfer microbiota and the post-transfer microbiota differed between the four groups. Pairwise comparisons were performed by fitting an analysis of Variance and implementing the Tukey's Honest Significant Difference method with the *aov* and *TukeyHSD* functions in R.

a) ASV Richness (with interaction)

<i>lm(asv_1_to_3 ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	-28.143	57.451	-0.490	0.629
Site of origin(urban)	106.571	81.248	1.312	0.202
Site of transfer(urban)	-7.257	89.002	-0.082	0.936
Site of origin(urban): site of transfer(urban)	-31.394	117.427	-0.267	0.791
F-statistic: 0.8507 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: -0.01687				

b) ASV Richness (without interaction)

<i>lm(asv_1_to_3 ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	-20.63	49.17	-0.420	0.678
Site of origin(urban)	91.54	57.56	1.590	0.124
Site of transfer(urban)	-25.29	56.97	-0.444	0.661
F-statistic: 1.288 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.02089				

c) ASV Richness (only site of origin)

<i>lm(asv_1_to_3 ~ site of origin, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	-31.17	42.39	-0.735	0.469
Site of origin(urban)	87.85	56.07	1.567	0.129
F-statistic: 2.455 on 1 and 26 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.05113				

d) ASV Richness (Multiple Comparisons of Means: Tukey Contrasts)

<i>TukeyHSD(aov(asv_1_to_3 ~ treatment, data))</i>				
Linear Hypotheses	diff	lwr	uppr	p adj
Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	-7.257143	-252.7798	238.2655	0.9997998
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural = 0	106.571429	-117.5591	330.7019	0.5646954
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	67.920635	-143.3916	279.2329	0.8117371
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban = 0	113.828571	-131.6941	359.3512	0.5846305
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban = 0	75.177778	-158.7021	309.0576	0.8117166
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural = 0	-38.650794	-249.9631	172.6615	0.9572053

e) Shannon Diversity (with interaction)

<i>lm(shannon_1_to_3 ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	-0.3849	0.5336	-0.721	0.478
Site of origin(urban)	1.1707	0.7546	1.551	0.134

Site of transfer(urban)	-0.4004	0.8267	-0.484	0.633
Site of origin(urban): site of transfer(urban)	-0.8348	1.0907	-0.765	0.451
F-statistic: 1.557 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.05824				

f) Shannon Diversity (without interaction)

<i>lm(shannon_1_to_3 ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate Std.	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	-0.1851	0.4615	-0.401	0.692
Site of origin(urban)	0.7710	0.5403	1.427	0.166
Site of transfer(urban)	-0.8799	0.5348	-1.645	0.112
F-statistic: 2.076 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.07384				

g) Shannon Diversity (Multiple Comparisons of Means: Tukey Contrasts)

<i>TukeyHSD(aov(shannon_1_to_3 ~ treatment, data))</i>				
Linear Hypotheses	diff	lwr	uppr	p adj
Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	-0.40036253	-2.6807983	1.880073	0.9618448
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural = 0	1.17067812	-0.9110654	3.252422	0.4241307
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	-0.06448849	-2.0271751	1.898198	0.9997252
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban = 0	1.57104064	-0.7093952	3.851476	0.2544024
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban = 0	0.33587403	-1.8364220	2.508170	0.9733677
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural = 0	-1.23516661	-3.1978533	0.727520	0.3278745

h) Faith's Phylogenetic diversity (with interaction)

<i>lm(faith_1_to_3 ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate Std.	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	0.007656	1.961622	0.004	0.997
Site of origin(urban)	2.200009	2.774152	0.793	0.436
Site of transfer(urban)	-1.753781	3.038931	-0.577	0.569
Site of origin(urban): site of transfer(urban)	0.475530	4.009479	0.119	0.907
F-statistic: 0.6057 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: -0.04581				

i) Faith's Phylogenetic diversity (without interaction)

<i>lm(faith_1_to_3 ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate Std.	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	-0.1062	1.6767	-0.063	0.950
Site of origin(urban)	2.4277	1.9630	1.237	0.228
Site of transfer(urban)	-1.4806	1.9429	-0.762	0.453
F-statistic: 0.9386 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: -0.00457				

j) Faith's Phylogenetic diversity (Multiple Comparisons of Means: Tukey Contrasts)

<i>TukeyHSD(aov(faith_1_to_3 ~ treatment, data))</i>				
Linear Hypotheses	diff	lwr	uppr	p adj
Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	-1.753781	-10.137003	6.629441	0.9379789
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural = 0	2.200009	-5.452791	9.852808	0.8568868
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.921757	-6.293372	8.136886	0.9846141
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban = 0	3.953790	-4.429432	12.337012	0.5711652
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban = 0	2.675538	-5.310146	10.661223	0.7922211
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural = 0	-1.278252	-8.493381	5.936877	0.9608618

Supplementary Table S4. Differences in alpha diversity between the post-transfer microbiota of bank voles of different experimental groups

Results from the linear regression models, carried out by the *lm* function in R ($p < 0.05$).

a) ASV Richness

<i>lm (ASV Richness ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	232.143	37.094	6.258	1.81e-06
Site of origin: U	113.714	52.459	2.168	0.0403 *
Site of transfer: U	3.657	57.466	0.064	0.9498
Interaction: U-U	-42.403	75.819	-0.559	0.5812
F-statistic: 2.145 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1209				

<i>lm (ASV Richness ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	242.29	31.90	7.595	5.98e-08
Site of origin: U	93.41	37.35	2.501	0.0193 *
Site of transfer: U	-20.70	36.97	-0.560	0.5805
F-statistic: 3.148 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1373				

<i>lm (ASV Richness ~ site of origin, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	233.67	27.57	8.476	5.88e-09
Site of origin: U	90.40	36.47	2.479	0.02 *
F-statistic: 6.144 on 1 and 26 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.16				

b) Shannon Diversity

<i>lm (Shannon Index ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	4.8399	0.3876	12.487	5.46e-12
Site of origin: U	1.2432	0.5482	2.268	0.0326 *
Site of transfer: U	-0.1320	0.6005	-0.220	0.8279
Interaction: U-U	-0.7446	0.7922	-0.940	0.3567
F-statistic: 2.384 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1333				

<i>lm (Shannon Index ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	5.0182	0.3373	14.879	6.29e-14
Site of origin: U	0.8867	0.3948	2.246	0.0338 *
Site of transfer: U	-0.5597	0.3908	-1.432	0.1645
F-statistic: 3.149 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1373				

<i>lm (Shannon Index ~ site of origin, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	4.7850	0.3013	15.88	6.7e-15
Site of origin: U	0.8051	0.3985	2.02	0.0538
F-statistic: 4.081 on 1 and 26 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1024				

c) Faith's Phylogenetic Diversity

<i>lm (Faith's PD~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	17.6274	1.2717	13.861	5.98e-13
Site of origin: U	2.7887	1.7984	1.551	0.134
Site of transfer: U	-0.2396	1.9701	-0.122	0.904
Interaction: U-U	-1.1603	2.5993	-0.446	0.659
F-statistic: 1.123 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.01353				

<i>lm (Faith's PD~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	17.9051	1.0912	16.409	6.79e-15
Site of origin: U	2.2332	1.2775	1.748	0.0927
Site of transfer: U	-0.9061	1.2644	-0.717	0.4802
F-statistic: 1.638 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.04513				

<i>lm (Faith's PD~ site of origin, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std. Error	T value	P value
Intercept	17.5276	0.9466	18.516	<2e-16
Site of origin: U	2.1011	1.2522	1.678	0.105
F-statistic: 2.815 on 1 and 26 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.06299				

Supplementary Table S5. Pairwise differences in alpha diversity between the post-transfer microbiota of bank voles

Pairwise comparisons were performed by fitting an analysis of Variance and implementing the Tukey's Honest Significant Difference method with the *aov* and *TukeyHSD* functions in R.

a) ASV Richness

Comparisons	Difference	Lower	Upper	<i>p</i> adjusted
Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural	3.657143	-154.86822	162.18251	0.9999047
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural	113.714286	-30.99891	258.42748	0.1611004
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural	74.968254	-61.46866	211.40516	0.4440745
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	110.057143	-48.46822	268.58251	0.2484255
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban	71.311111	-79.69688	222.31910	0.5701536
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural	-38.746032	-175.18294	97.69088	0.8612208

b) Shannon diversity

Comparisons	Difference	Lower	Upper	<i>p</i> adjusted
Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural	-0.1319602	-1.7884273	1.5245068	0.9961493
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural	1.2431686	-0.2689720	2.7553093	0.1339989
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural	0.3666311	-1.0590288	1.7922909	0.8923731
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	1.3751289	-0.2813382	3.0315959	0.1285399
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban	0.4985913	-1.0793250	2.0765076	0.8193246
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural	-0.8765375	-2.3021974	0.5491223	0.3475513

c) Faith's phylogenetic diversity

Comparisons	Difference	Lower	Upper	<i>p</i> adjusted
Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural	-0.2395793	-5.674320	5.195161	0.9993383
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural	2.7886813	-2.172535	7.749898	0.4245267
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural	1.3888085	-3.288671	6.066289	0.8448750
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	3.0282606	-2.406480	8.463001	0.4320556
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban	1.6283878	-3.548634	6.805409	0.8213103
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural	-1.3998728	-6.077353	3.277607	0.8417963

Supplementary Table S6. Differences in beta diversity between pre-transfer microbiota of urban and rural bank voles and variance tests according to site of origin and site of transfer

Results from the *adonis* and *betadisper* functions ($p < 0.05$). When the variance is significantly different, it is stated between brackets which group has higher levels (U: Urban, R: Rural).

<i>adonis</i> (formula = Bray-Curtis distance~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site origin	1	0.7127	0.71268	2.5777	0.0902	3e-04 ***	0.7021
Residuals	26	7.1886	0.27648		0.9098		
Total	27	7.9013			1.0000		
<i>adonis</i> (formula = Jaccard distance~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site origin	1	0.6808	0.68079	1.8907	0.06779	3e-04 ***	0.6991
Residuals	26	9.3620	0.36008		0.93221		
Total	27	10.0428			1.00000		
<i>adonis</i> (formula = Weighted UniFrac distance ~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site origin	1	0.0002923	0.00029228	1.4418	0.05254	0.1791	0.5792
Residuals	26	0.0052707	0.00020272		0.94746		
Total	27	0.0055629			1.00000		
<i>adonis</i> (formula = Unweighted UniFrac distance~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site origin	1	0.4871	0.48715	2.1669	0.07693	2e-04 ***	0.005603 ** (U<R)
Residuals	26	5.8451	0.22481		0.92307		
Total	27	6.3323			1.00000		

Supplementary Table S7. Pairwise distances in beta diversity change between experimental groups

Results from the linear regression models, carried out by the *lm* function in R ($p < 0.05$). This method was used to test whether the change in beta diversity between the pre-transfer microbiota and the post-transfer microbiota differed between the four groups. Pairwise comparisons were performed by fitting an analysis of Variance and implementing the Tukey's Honest Significant Difference method with the *aov* and *TukeyHSD* functions in R.

a) Bray-Curtis (with interaction)

<i>lm (bray_1_to_3 ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.61869	0.04236	14.605	1.94e-13
Site of origin(urban)	0.15324	0.05991	2.558	0.0173
Site of transfer(urban)	0.12538	0.06563	1.911	0.0681
Site of origin(urban): site of transfer(urban)	-0.17219	0.08658	-1.989	0.0583
F-statistic: 2.46 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1396				

b) Bray-Curtis (without interaction)

<i>lm (bray_1_to_3 ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.65991	0.03907	16.891	3.48e-15
Site of origin(urban)	0.07081	0.04574	1.548	0.134
Site of transfer(urban)	0.02646	0.04527	0.585	0.564
F-statistic: 1.532 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.0379				

c) Bray-Curtis (only site of origin)

<i>lm (bray_1_to_3 ~ site of origin, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.67093	0.03378	19.864	<2e-16
Site of origin(urban)	0.07467	0.04468	1.671	0.107
F-statistic: 2.793 on 1 and 26 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.06226				

d) Bray-Curtis (Multiple Comparisons of Means: Tukey Contrasts)

<i>TukeyHSD (aov (bray_1_to_3 ~ treatment, data))</i>				
Linear Hypotheses	diff	lwr	uppr	p adj
Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.12538042	-0.05565496	0.3064158	0.2502989
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.15323922	-0.01202272	0.3185011	0.0759906
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.10643165	-0.04937880	0.2622421	0.2610563
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban = 0	0.02785880	-0.15317658	0.2088942	0.9737252
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban = 0	-0.01894877	-0.19139933	0.1535018	0.9900781
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural = 0	-0.04680757	-0.20261801	0.1090029	0.8403106

e) Jaccard (with interaction)

<i>lm (jaccard_1_to_3 ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.74599	0.01773	42.065	<2e-16
Site of origin(urban)	0.01821	0.02508	0.726	0.475

Site of transfer(urban)	0.02802	0.02747	1.020	0.318
Site of origin(urban): site of transfer(urban)	-0.04311	0.03625	-1.189	0.246
F-statistic: 0.4865 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: -0.06051				

f) Jaccard (without interaction)

<i>lm (jaccard_1_to_3 ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.756305	0.015594	48.499	<2e-16
Site of origin(urban)	-0.002425	0.018257	-0.133	0.895
Site of transfer(urban)	0.003259	0.018070	0.180	0.858
F-statistic: 0.02209 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: -0.07809				

g) Jaccard (Multiple Comparisons of Means: Tukey Contrasts)

<i>TukeyHSD (aov (jaccard_1_to_3 ~ treatment, data))</i>				
Linear Hypotheses	diff	lwr	uppr	p adj
Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.028024479	-0.04776391	0.10381287	0.7394747
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.018212675	-0.05097234	0.08739769	0.8856502
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.003126432	-0.06210183	0.06835469	0.9991504
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban = 0	-0.009811804	-0.08560019	0.06597659	0.9840103
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban = 0	-0.024898048	-0.09709250	0.04729641	0.7776926
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural = 0	-0.015086243	-0.08031450	0.05014202	0.9186520

h) Weighted UniFrac (with interaction)

<i>lm (wUniFrac_1_to_3 ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.163879	0.027699	5.916	4.19e-06
Site of origin(urban)	0.097812	0.039173	2.497	0.0198 *
Site of transfer(urban)	0.006871	0.042912	0.160	0.8741
Site of origin(urban): site of transfer(urban)	-0.048229	0.056616	-0.852	0.4027
F-statistic: 2.613 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.152				

i) Weighted UniFrac (without interaction)

<i>lm (wUniFrac_1_to_3 ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.17542	0.02402	7.302	1.19e-07
Site of origin(urban)	0.07472	0.02813	2.657	0.0135 *
Site of transfer(urban)	-0.02083	0.02784	-0.748	0.4612
F-statistic: 3.597 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1613				

j) Weighted UniFrac (only site of origin)

<i>lm (wUniFrac_1_to_3 ~ site of origin, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.16674	0.02086	7.993	1.8e-08
Site of origin(urban)	0.07168	0.02760	2.598	0.0153 *
F-statistic: 6.748 on 1 and 26 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.1755				

k) Weighted UniFrac (Multiple Comparisons of Means: Tukey Contrasts)

<i>TukeyHSD (aov (wUniFrac_1_to_3 ~ treatment, data))</i>				
Linear Hypotheses	diff	lwr	uppr	p adj

Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.006870975	-0.11150548	0.12524743	0.9984963
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.097811507	-0.01025092	0.20587394	0.0859567
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.056453578	-0.04542866	0.15833581	0.4368540
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban = 0	0.090940533	-0.02743593	0.20931699	0.1756769
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban = 0	0.049582603	-0.06318037	0.16234557	0.6248546
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural = 0	-0.041357929	-0.14324016	0.06052431	0.6811362

l) Unweighted UniFrac (with interaction)

<i>lm (unwUniFrac_1_to_3 ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.416245	0.022107	18.828	7.02e-16
Site of origin(urban)	0.027492	0.031264	0.879	0.388
Site of transfer(urban)	0.017493	0.034248	0.511	0.614
Site of origin(urban): site of transfer(urban)	-0.003048	0.045786	-0.067	0.947
F-statistic: 0.7032 on 3 and 24 df, Adjusted R-squared: -0.0341				

m) Unweighted UniFrac (without interaction)

<i>lm (unwUniFrac_1_to_3 ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data)</i>				
Coefficients	Estimate	Std.	T value	P value
Intercept	0.41697	0.01889	22.070	<2e-16
Site of origin(urban)	0.02603	0.02212	1.177	0.250
Site of transfer(urban)	0.01574	0.02189	0.719	0.479
F-statistic: 1.096 on 2 and 25 df, Adjusted R-squared: 0.007072				

n) Unweighted UniFrac (Multiple Comparisons of Means: Tukey Contrasts)

<i>TukeyHSD (aov (unwUniFrac_1_to_3 ~ treatment, data))</i>				
Linear Hypotheses	diff	lwr	uppr	p adj
Rural-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.01749267	-0.07698540	0.11197074	0.9557258
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.02749249	-0.05875380	0.11373878	0.8154555
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Rural = 0	0.04193713	-0.03937665	0.12325091	0.4980003
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban = 0	0.00999982	-0.08447825	0.10447789	0.9911074
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban = 0	0.02444446	-0.06555340	0.11444232	0.8760702
Urban-Urban vs. Urban-Rural = 0	0.01444464	-0.06686914	0.09575842	0.9605649

Supplementary Table S8. Differences in beta diversity between the post-transfer microbiota of bank voles of different experimental groups

Results from the *adonis* and *betadisper* functions ($p < 0.05$). When the variance is significantly different, it is stated between brackets which group has higher levels (U: Urban, R: Rural).

a) In terms of site of origin

<i>adonis</i> (formula = Bray-Curtis distance~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site origin	1	0.3884	0.38840	1.4666	0.05339	0.078	0.03148 * (U>R)
Residuals	26	6.8857	0.26483		0.94661		
Total	27	7.2741			1.00000		
<i>adonis</i> (formula = Jaccard distance~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site origin	1	0.4386	0.43860	1.253	0.04598	0.0948	0.02991 * (U>R)
Residuals	26	9.1012	0.35005		0.95402		
Total	27	9.5398			1.00000		
<i>adonis</i> (formula = Weighted UniFrac distance ~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site origin	1	0.0002738	0.00027382	1.8029	0.06485	0.122	0.01801 * (U>R)
Residuals	26	0.0039488	0.00015188		0.93515		
Total	27	0.0042226			1.00000		
<i>adonis</i> (formula = Unweighted UniFrac distance~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site origin	1	0.2979	0.29790	1.2971	0.04752	0.0436 *	0.8331
Residuals	26	5.9715	0.22967		0.95248		
Total	27	6.2694			1.00000		

b) In terms of site of transfer

<i>adonis</i> (formula = Bray-Curtis distance~ site of transfer, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site transfer	1	0.4262	0.42620	1.6182	0.05859	0.0381 *	0.5736
Residuals	26	6.8479	0.26338		0.94141		
Total	27	7.2741			1.00000		
<i>adonis</i> (formula = Jaccard distance~ site of transfer, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site transfer	1	0.4884	0.48844	1.403	0.0512	0.0334 *	0.5789
Residuals	26	9.0514	0.34813		0.9488		
Total	27	9.5398			1.0000		
<i>adonis</i> (formula = Weighted UniFrac distance ~ site of transfer, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site transfer	1	0.0002335	0.00023351	1.5219	0.0553	0.1722	0.8869
Residuals	26	0.0039891	0.00015343		0.9447		
Total	27	0.0042226			1.0000		
<i>adonis</i> (formula = Unweighted UniFrac distance~ site of transfer, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>

	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site transfer	1	0.2777	0.27768	1.2049	0.04429	0.0996	0.8185
Residuals	26	5.9917	0.23045		0.95571		
Total	27	6.2694			1.00000		

c) In terms of treatment

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Bray-Curtis Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")							
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment	
Site origin	1	0.4324	0.05944	1.6849	0.0286 *	Interaction: non-significant	
Site transfer	1	0.4702	0.06464	1.8323	0.0155 *		
Residual	25	6.4155	0.88197				
Total	27	7.2741	1.00000				
<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Jaccard Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")							
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment	
Site origin	1	0.4739	0.04967	1.3812	0.0379 *	Interaction: non-significant	
Site transfer	1	0.5237	0.05490	1.5265	0.0132 *		
Residual	25	8.5775	0.89913				
Total	27	9.5398	1.00000				
<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Weighted UniFrac Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")							
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment	
Site origin	1	0.0002938	0.06959	1.9880	0.0970	Interaction: non-significant	
Site transfer	1	0.0002535	0.06004	1.7153	0.1342		
Residual	25	0.0036953	0.87511				
Total	27	0.0042226	1.00000				
<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Unweighted UniFrac Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")							
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment	
Site origin	1	0.3004	0.04791	1.3194	0.0379 *	Interaction: non-significant	
Site transfer	1	0.2801	0.04469	1.2306	0.0818		
Residual	25	5.6914	0.90780				
Total	27	6.2694	1.00000				

Supplementary Table S9. Pairwise differences in beta diversity between the post-transfer microbiota of bank voles

Results from the *pairwise.adonis* function under the PAIRWISEADONIS package in R with the Benjamin-Hochberg adjustment for *p* values ($q < 0.05$).

a) Bray-Curtis

<i>pairwise.adonis (Bray Distance, metadata\$treatment, p.adjust.m="BH", perm=9999)</i>						
Pairs	Df	SumsOfSqs	F.Model	R ²	<i>p</i>	<i>p</i> adjusted
Rural-Rural vs. Urban-Rural	1	0.3751665	1.429945	0.10647437	0.1111	0.18228
Rural-Rural vs. Urban-Urban	1	0.2813892	1.075879	0.07136429	0.3332	0.33320
Rural-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.3757682	1.704282	0.14561187	0.0568	0.17040
Urban-Rural vs. Urban-Urban	1	0.3674472	1.306434	0.08535195	0.1519	0.18228
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.5765618	2.324027	0.18857691	0.0024	0.01440 *
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.3302460	1.323582	0.09934132	0.1515	0.18228

b) Jaccard

<i>pairwise.adonis (Jaccard Distance, metadata\$treatment, p.adjust.m="BH", perm=9999)</i>						
Pairs	Df	SumsOfSqs	F.Model	R ²	<i>p</i>	<i>P</i> adjusted
Rural-Rural vs. Urban-Rural	1	0.4254364	1.220648	0.09232889	0.1427	0.2022
Rural-Rural vs. Urban-Urban	1	0.3629512	1.045787	0.06950694	0.3301	0.3301
Rural-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.4630240	1.481008	0.12899636	0.0325	0.0975
Urban-Rural vs. Urban-Urban	1	0.4256258	1.171564	0.07722104	0.1685	0.2022
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.6038399	1.800506	0.15257869	0.0024	0.01440 *
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.4133745	1.230840	0.09302808	0.1322	0.2022

c) Weighted UniFrac

<i>pairwise.adonis (Weighted UniFrac Distance, metadata\$treatment, p.adjust.m="BH", perm=9999)</i>						
Pairs	Df	SumsOfSqs	F.Model	R ²	<i>p</i>	<i>P</i> adjusted
Rural-Rural vs. Urban-Rural	1	0.0001354	1.0055374	0.07731610	0.4250	0.4274
Rural-Rural vs. Urban-Urban	1	0.0001850	1.1380936	0.07518077	0.3756	0.4274
Rural-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.0001351	2.4125038	0.19436077	0.0330	0.0990
Urban-Rural vs. Urban-Urban	1	0.0001935	0.8852412	0.05947107	0.4274	0.4274
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.0003354	2.4958912	0.19973695	0.0182	0.0990
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.0002335	1.3982069	0.10435776	0.1936	0.3872

d) Unweighted UniFrac

<i>pairwise.adonis (Unweighted UniFrac Distance, metadata\$treatment, p.adjust.m="BH", perm=9999)</i>						
Pairs	Df	SumsOfSqs	F.Model	R ²	<i>p</i>	<i>P</i> adjusted
Rural-Rural vs. Urban-Rural	1	0.3111750	1.399696	0.10445728	0.0321	0.13590
Rural-Rural vs. Urban-Urban	1	0.2857435	1.208527	0.07946376	0.1045	0.17910
Rural-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.2658744	1.184414	0.10589862	0.1194	0.17910
Urban-Rural vs. Urban-Urban	1	0.2594311	1.134506	0.07496157	0.1732	0.20784
Urban-Rural vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.2915985	1.365132	0.12011582	0.0453	0.13590
Urban-Urban vs. Rural-Urban	1	0.2343548	1.012184	0.07778741	0.4191	0.41910

Table S10. Differences in beta diversity between the abundant, rare and newly gained ASVs that comprise the post-transfer microbiota of bank voles of different experimental groups

Results from the *adonis2*, *adonis* and *betadisper* functions ($p < 0.05$).

a) Abundant ASVs

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Bray-Curtis Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")						
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.4057	0.06051	1.7255	0.0421 *	Interaction: non-significant
Site transfer	1	0.4695	0.07001	1.9965	0.0163 *	
Residual	25	5.8785	0.87672			
Total	27	6.7052	1.00000			

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Jaccard Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")						
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.4550	0.05029	1.4037	0.0600	Interaction: non-significant
Site transfer	1	0.5310	0.05870	1.6384	0.0159 *	
Residual	25	8.1030	0.89562			
Total	27	9.0474	1.00000			

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Weighted UniFrac Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")						
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.02578	0.04082	1.1234	0.3145	Interaction: non-significant
Site transfer	1	0.03347	0.05301	1.4587	0.1954	
Residual	25	0.57365	0.90851			
Total	27	0.63142	1.00000			

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Unweighted UniFrac Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")						
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.04890	0.04306	1.1865	0.2907	Interaction: non-significant
Site transfer	1	0.05232	0.04607	1.26960	0.2394	
Residual	25	1.03037	0.90727			
Total	27	1.13569	1.00000			

b) Rare ASVs

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Bray-Curtis Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")						
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.5065	0.04911	1.3548	0.0102 *	Interaction: non-significant
Site transfer	1	0.4542	0.04403	1.2148	0.0531	
Residual	25	9.3465	0.90624			
Total	27	10.3135	1.00000			

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Jaccard Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")						
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.5138	0.04384	1.1978	0.0089 **	

Site transfer	1	0.4790	0.04087	1.1166	0.0537	Interaction: non- significant
Residual	25	10.7244	0.91491			
Total	27	11.7219	1.00000			

adonis2(formula = Weighted UniFrac Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")

	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.04866	0.04928	1.3362	0.1969	Interaction: non- significant
Site transfer	1	0.03059	0.03098	0.8399	0.4841	
Residual	25	0.91042	0.92199			
Total	27	0.98746	1.00000			

adonis2(formula = Unweighted UniFrac Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")

	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.2458	0.05718	1.5656	0.0129 *	Interaction: non- significant
Site transfer	1	0.1314	0.03057	0.8372	0.8125	
Residual	25	3.9251	0.91296			
Total	27	4.2993	1.00000			

adonis(formula = Unweighted UniFrac distance~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999) | *betadisp*

	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site transfer	1	0.2428	0.24276	1.5559	0.05646	0.0132 *	0.5748
Residuals	26	4.0565	0.15602		0.94354		
Total	27	4.2993			1.00000		

c) Newly gained ASVs

adonis2(formula = Bray-Curtis Distance ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")

	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin : Site transfer	1	0.5597	0.04316	1.1786	0.0277 *	Interaction: significant
Residual	24	11.3972	0.87890			
Total	27	12.9676	1.00000			

adonis2(formula = Jaccard Distance ~ site of origin * site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")

	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin : Site transfer	1	0.5352	0.04049	1.0998	0.0248 *	Interaction: significant
Residual	24	11.6799	0.88355			
Total	27	13.2193	1.00000			

adonis2(formula = Weighted UniFrac Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")

	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.011598	0.04013	1.1075	0.3211	Interaction: non- significant
Site transfer	1	0.015647	0.05414	1.4942	0.1127	
Residual	25	0.261806	0.90592			
Total	27	0.288994	1.00000			

<i>adonis2</i> (formula = Unweighted UniFrac Distance ~ site of origin + site of transfer, data, perm = 9999, by = "margin")						
	Df	SumOfSqs	R2	F	p	Comment
Site origin	1	0.3236	0.05004	1.3796	0.0503	Interaction: non- significant
Site transfer	1	0.2705	0.04183	1.1533	0.2064	
Residual	25	5.8640	0.90667			
Total	27	6.4676	1.00000			

<i>adonis</i> (formula = Unweighted UniFrac distance~ site of origin, data , perm = 9999)							<i>betadisp</i>
	Df	SumOfSqs	MeanSqs	F.Model	R2	p	p
Site transfer	1	0.3331	0.33313	1.4119	0.05151	0.0409 *	0.3301
Residuals	26	6.1345	0.23594		0.94849		
Total	27	6.4676			1.00000		

Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure S1. Change in alpha diversity throughout the experiment (ASV Richness)

The inter-individual change in alpha diversity between the pre-transfer and post-transfer gut microbiota is shown on the left (A), with positive and negative values corresponding to an increase and decrease, respectively. A trend towards higher accumulation of alpha diversity is visible in urban animals in comparison to rural animals. The alpha diversity of the post-transfer gut microbiota is shown on the right (B), with urban animals having on average higher levels of alpha diversity.

Supplementary Figure S2. Magnitude and direction of change in beta diversity between experimental groups (Bray-Curtis and Jaccard metrics)

Turn-over rates in the relative abundances of taxa (Bray-Curtis metric, A) were lower in animals originating from rural forests and transferred to rural forests (A). When rare taxa are taken into account (Jaccard metric), the turn-over rates are equal for all four experimental groups (B). Changes for both metrics are directional (C, D) with each experimental group having distinct microbiota compositions. The gut microbiota of animals undergoing translocation treatments that shift between urban and rural forests do not match the transfer environment but merely transit into 'alternative states'.

Supplementary Figure S3. Individual taxa barplots displaying the bacterial families in the post-transfer gut microbiota arranged according to experimental group

Relative abundances of the most important families per individual are visualised which shows that there are only minor differences between members of different experimental groups. In general, the post-transfer gut microbiota of wild bank voles is always highly represented (>80%) by three families: *Muribaculaceae*, *Lactobacillaceae* and *Lachnospiraceae*. Each vertical bar represents one sample.

Supplementary Figure S4. Venn diagram displaying overlap of ASVs between post-transfer microbiota in terms of experimental groups

Around half of the total 1931 ASVs present in the total post-transfer gut microbiota is only present in one of the experimental groups while only 16.9% of the total ASVs are shared among all experimental groups. Despite this, the latter accounts for 83.5% of the total sequences. This shows that the majority of ASVs are rare and group specific.

Supplementary Figure S5. Heat trees for abundant ASVs in the post-transfer microbiota

The figures show that the phylogenetic identity of abundant ASVs is similar per experimental group. Within each heat tree, larger number of ASVs are represented by darker colours and larger node sizes. Direct comparison between the experimental groups in terms of node/branch sizes is not possible since each heat tree represents a different number of ASVs (see ASV count).

Figure S6. Heat trees for the rare ASVs in the post-transfer microbiota
 The figures show that the phylogenetic identity of rare ASVs is similar per experimental group. Within each heat tree, larger number of ASVs are represented by darker colours and larger node sizes. Direct comparison between the experimental groups in terms of node/branch sizes is not possible since each heat tree represents a different number of ASVs (see ASV count).

Supplementary Figure S7. Heat trees for newly gained ASVs in the post-transfer microbiota

The figures show that the phylogenetic identity of newly gained ASVs is similar per experimental group. Within each heat tree, larger number of ASVs are represented by darker colours and larger node sizes. Direct comparison between the experimental groups in terms of node/branch sizes is not possible since each heat tree represents a different number of ASVs (see ASV count).